

VOLUMETRIC PROPERTIES OF ASPHALT CONCRETE MADE FROM ZANZIBAR CORALLINE AGGREGATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the unusual engineering properties of coralline aggregates used for asphalt binder course production during the rehabilitation of Zanzibar airport (Tanzania). The geotechnical and geomechanical properties of the coralline aggregates, asphalt concrete mix design and the volumetric parameters achieved during mix design are discussed. Asphalt concrete production and the placing procedures are also discussed. Finally, the paper recommends the measures to be taken when using coralline aggregates for asphalt concrete production.

INTRODUCTION

Zanzibar is an island located in the Indian Ocean and is part of the United Republic of Tanzania. The Zanzibar airport runway was upgraded in the year 2010 to conform with code 4E in line with ICAO specifications whereby the runway was widened from 30 m to 45 m by extending the shoulder width by 7.5 m on either side of the centerline bringing the total width of the runway to 60 m $[(45+2*(7.5\text{ m}))]$. The runway length was also extended by 560 m from 2460 m to 3200 m. The pavement rehabilitation as per project design called for 60 mm of binder course and 40 mm of wearing course, bringing the total thickness of the placed asphalt to be 100 mm (minimum thickness). Depending on the severity of pavement distress, in some locations, two layers of binder course having a nominal maximum aggregate size of 20 mm was placed. The project design called for binder course to be produced from coralline aggregates available along the Zanzibar coast and the wearing course to be produced from massive granite gneiss aggregate from the mainland.

MATERIALS CHARACTERISATION

Aggregates

The aggregates for asphalt concrete bound base were obtained after crushing the coralline rock, which was quarried within the airport vicinity. The aggregates were crushed into three-grain sizes, namely 0/6, 6/14, and 14/25. This coralline material was explicitly crushed for the production of the bound bituminous base.

The coralline aggregates were tested in the site laboratory to ascertain that the aggregates are conforming to project specifications. The shape of the aggregates was determined using the flakiness index test. The mechanical properties were tested using the aggregate crushing value test. The durability was tested using the water absorption [*indirect indicator test*] and magnesium sulphate soundness test, the deleterious matter was tested using the sand equivalent test. The stripping potential of the aggregates was quantified using a special procedure given in the technical specifications whereby one hundred fifty aggregate particles were coated with 4% of bitumen (by weight) and immersed in water for 48 hours. The stripping was evaluated visually by counting the number of aggregate particles that stripped. The aggregates were deemed to fail the stripping test if more than six pieces out of the one hundred fifty pieces showed any sign of stripping. The summary of the test results for the coralline aggregates is shown in Table 1.

It is worth noting that the project specification called for maximum water absorption of 6%, which is contrary to normally specified maximum water absorption of 2%-3% [*Section 4200 of Tanzania MoW Standard Specifications for Road Works, 2000*]. Since high water

absorption is an inherent characteristic property of coralline aggregates, the project specification was relaxed to ensure that the local aggregates available within the project vicinity can be used for asphalt concrete production. This relaxation of the project specifications is one of the pragmatics and value engineering

approaches that is currently advocated in the construction industry. Thus, sometimes the normally specified parameters can be relaxed to ensure that the materials available within the project vicinity are utilised for the project but without sacrificing the quality and the durability of pavement.

Table 1: geotechnical properties of the coralline material

Parameter	Result	Project Specification
Specific gravity	2.372	
Water absorption	3.8%	6% maximum
ACV	29%	30% maximum
Magnesium sulphate soundness	7%	18% maximum
Coating and stripping	Pass	Ok, visual inspection of the particle
Flakiness index	28	30% maximum

From the test results given Table 1, it is clear that the coralline material used for asphalt concrete production can be termed as marginal quality material.

MIX DESIGN

Three crushed aggregate size, namely 0/6, 6/14, and 14/25 were used for asphalt concrete production. In order to reduce the absorption of the binder, it was technically deemed necessary to add 10% of natural sand in the mix. The four aggregate fractions, namely 0/6, 6/14, 14/25, and natural sand from the cold-bins, were passed through the hot-bins, thereby the grading modified at the hot bins screening unit. The batching plant used for asphalt concrete production was equipment with cyclone dust collector; thus, the filler was extracted from the 0/6 and stored in the bag-house. In the hot-bins, the coralline aggregates were screened into five fractions, namely 25/14, 14/10, 10/6, 6/0, and inert filler, which was stored in the baghouse. The 0/6 fraction was combination of both crushed and natural sand. The hot-bins grading for all five fractions is shown in Figure 1.

The five fractions, including the inert filler from the hot-bins, were combined to get the specified all-in aggregates to get the aggregate design structure, which complied with the project specifications.

The resultant aggregate design structure, as well as the specified envelope, is shown in Figure 1.

The binder used was straight-run bitumen penetration grade 60/70 complying with the requirements of AASHTO M20-70. The use of less-stiffer bitumen 60/70 was found to be ideal for the tropical climate to avoid the possibility of having the top-down cracking caused by differential binder stiffness due to age-hardening, thus creating a steep gradient of binder viscosity.

Figure 1: the hot bins grading, bound base envelope and Aggregate Design Structure

The aggregate design structure was established by combined all five aggregate fractions from the hot-bins. The Marshall specimens were moulded using the

standard procedures outlined in Asphalt Institute Manual Series 2 (MS 2) 5th Edition. The asphalt sample was oven-aged for two hours before compaction of Marshall briquette to depict the actual delay in the field before placing. This ageing procedure allowed the coralline aggregate to absorb binder. The Marshall specimens were moulded with bitumen content ranging from 4.0%-6.0%. The bitumen content was increased stepwise at an interval of 0.5%. The aggregate and binder were mixed at 160°C corresponding a binder viscosity of about 0.17±0.02 Pa.s and was compacted at 150 °C corresponding to a binder viscosity of about 0.28±0.03 Pa.s as derived from viscosity-temperature relationship graph using viscosity test results from the supplier’s test certificate. The viscosity-temperature relationship for the binder used for asphalt concrete production is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Viscosity temperature relationship for 60/70 pen grade bitumen

For each moulded specimen, the volumetric data were determined by either calculation or directly by weighing. The test results represent an average of four-Marshall specimen compacted with 75 blows at the same bitumen content. The target was to achieve a mix with 3-5% of air void using 75 Marshall blows. The aggregate design structure was selected to ensure that particle-to-particle contact is achieved so as get a mix that has sufficient shear strength mobilised by inter-particle friction. The graphical presentation of the achieved mix volumetric parameters during

asphalt concrete mix design as well as during plant trial is shown in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3: binder content versus bulk density

As can be seen from Figure 3, during a plant trial run, the density of the mix was found to be higher compared to the achieved density during mix design. During the mix design, the peak density was estimated to be 2.213 g/cm³ at 6% binder content, during plant trial, the density increased to a peak of 2.278 g/cm³ [2.94% increase in density] at 5.2% binder content. The increase in density is largely hypothesised to be due to the high absorption of coralline aggregate. It is further postulated that the attrition of aggregate and collision during heating and mixing produced additional ultra-fine particles which acted like asphalt extender. Coralline aggregates are soft, the interparticle collision during mixing led to breakage of some particles, thereby changed and improved the aggregate grading. Therefore, the packing of the aggregate was improved, leading to increase in density of the mix at lower binder content since the ultra-fine particle generated during mixing acted like bitumen extender thereby reducing the binder demand.

It can be seen that the G_{mb} increased by 2.94%, implying that the air void also decreased by the same margin. However, it can be seen that the binder content, which gives 4% air void during mix design and trial is almost the same [Figure 4]. This was so due to an increase in G_{mm} . The

increase in G_{mm} was caused by high absorption of binder, which was aggravated by storing the asphalt concrete at an elevated temperature up to 6 hours after production. [Figure 10].

The target air void was in the range of 3-5%, the target being to select the binder content at 4% air void [the median of 3-5]. It can be seen from Figure 4 that the binder content at 4% air void based on the mix design was 5.0% while the results from plant trial the binder content which gives 4% air void was found to be 4.9%. Despite the significant increase in density, the air voids were not affected much since the increase was compensated by the increase in G_{mm} value.

Figure 4: air-void and binder content

Voids in mineral aggregates is a function air void and the density of the compacted mix. The VMA at 5% binder content was 11.5% during mix design, while during plant trial, the VMA increased to 14.6% [an increase of 3.1%]. The increase in VMA was due to increase in G_{mm} , which changed the air voids of the original mix as computed during the mix design stage. It is also hypothesised that the change in VMA is likely to be due to the change in the grading of the aggregate design structure during mixing.

The VFB of the plant trial increased compared to the values recorded during the mix design. The increase in VFB was due to the apparent increase in VMA value

since the increase in VMA is associated with an increase in VFB, which is computed using equation 1.

$$VFB = \frac{VMA - va}{VMA} \dots (1)$$

Figure 5: VMA and binder content

Figure 6: VFB and binder content

The stability of the mix increased as the binder content increased to a peak value of 18.3 kN at 5.3% binder content. Test results from the plant trial showed a trend of increasing as the binder content increased. The stability of the plant trial was consistently lower than that recorded during mix design, but this was not considered as an issue since the values recorded were still above the minimum value of 8 kN given in the project specifications.

Figure 8: Stability and binder content

Figure 9: Flow versus binder content

The flow of the mix normally increases as the binder content increases. During mix design, this pattern of monotonical increase of flow as binder content increases was observed. However, this pattern was not observed during plant trial. It is postulated that the mix became insensitive to flow due to an increase in the ultrafine particle, which was generated during mixing, thus increasing the filler-binder ratio leading to an increase in stiffness of the mix. It is worth mentioning that the flow measured during the plant trial was well above the specified minimum value of 2 mm. The flow versus binder content is shown in Figure 9.

SELECTION OF OPTIMUM BINDER CONTENT

The optimum binder content was selected based on critical two parameters which

influence the performance of the hot mix asphalt, namely air voids and voids in mineral aggregates (VMA). The air voids in the mix is an important parameter in regard to the permanent deformation. Excess air voids lead to the rapid oxidation of the binder leading embrittlement of the mix while an insufficient amount of air voids may lead to permanent deformation and shoving of the asphalt concrete. Therefore, the analysis was based on the fact that the binder content should be selected such that the mix will retain at least 3% air voids during the entire life of the pavement, in other words, the mix should stabilise with air voids of at least 3% to guarantee the long-term performance of the airport pavement. Furthermore, the asphalt binder content was selected to ensure that sufficient film thickness of binder of more than 6 microns is achieved to guarantee the durability of the mix. The optimum binder content, based on the mix design data, was selected on dry-leg of the VMA curve to ensure that the mix will not exhibit plastic flow and/or permanent deformation. Based on this analysis, the binder of 5.0% was selected as the initial optimum binder content based on the mix design. During the plant trial, the VMA curve changed such that the 5% air void plotted on the wet-leg of VMA curve. This was not considered to be an issue since the VMA increased, suggesting that the volume occupied by the binder increased too. The increase in binder content usually is associated with improved durability of the mix.

The plant trial carried out to verify that the laboratory mix can be used for full-scale production of the bound bituminous base. The trial plant results showed that the binder absorption was high ranging from 1.50-1.94% [compare this with normally specified maximum binder absorption of 0.8%] and was difficult to achieve the requirement of the VFB consistently. Based on the analysis of the plant data and higher binder absorption of coralline aggregate, the binder content was increased from 5.0% to 5.2% corresponding to effective binder content of about 3.74% which was close to the recommended minimum binder of 4%. The summary of the volumetric

parameters at the adjusted optimum binder content of 5.2% is shown in Table 2. It can be seen from Table 2 that the binder content was selected at 3.5% air void, this was not considered to be an issue owing to the fact that the airport pavement rutting is not considered to be a concern,

but the durability of the mix is a more important parameter to be considered during the mix design of the airport pavement.

Table 2: Summary of volumetric at optimum binder content for base mix

Mix Properties	Value	Spec
Bitumen Content %	5.2	4-7
VMA	14.7	
Air Voids	3.5	3-5
VFB	73	67-77
Density, Gmb	2270 kg/m ³	
Stability	17.5 kN	>8 kN
Flow	2.6	>4 mm
Immersion Index	92%	

ASPHALT CONCRETE PRODUCTION, PLACING AND COMPACTION

The asphalt was mixed using a batch-type mixing plant with a maximum rated capacity of 160 tonnes/hour. To compensate for the expected temperature loss during short term storage at the plant, and storage at the stockpile for about 4-6 hours, the aggregates were heated to about 160-170 °C. The plant was capable of mixing up to a batch weight of 2 tons; since the specific gravity of the coralline material is low, it was not possible to mix two tones per batch; thus only 1.6 tons per batch were mixed suggesting that the loss of plant efficiency due to use of lightweight coralline material was about 20%. Therefore, the plant was operating at a capacity of 90-120 tons/hour instead of 160 ton/hour suggesting that the use of the lightweight coralline aggregates for asphalt production can reduce the efficiency of the plant for about 20-30%.

The asphalt production commenced 2-4 prior to placing. During this period, the asphalt was kept at an elevated temperature which promoted binder absorption. The higher binder absorption was associated with an increase in G_{mm} and bulk density of the marshall briquette (G_{mb}). The effect of keeping the asphalt made from the coralline aggregates at the

elevated temperature up to five hours (5) led to an increase in G_{mm} and G_{mb} of the asphalt (Figure 3 and 10).

The laboratory study was carried out so as to establish the effect of keeping the coralline asphalt at an elevated temperature for about 4-6 hours. The study established that by keeping the asphalt at an elevated temperature for 6 hours increased the maximum theoretical density from 2365 kg/m³ to 2416 kg/m³ suggesting that the air voids increased by about 2%.

Figure 10: the effect of aging on maximum theoretical density

COMPACTION

The compaction was carried out using a rolling pattern which was established

during the trial section. The asphalt temperature was recorded immediately after mixing, prior to laying (before tipping) and continuously monitored during compaction. The recorded mat cooling rate during binder course laying is shown in Figure 11 modelled using a polynomial model of four degrees. Using asphalt mat cooling model shown in Figure 11, the asphalt temperature at any time interval was accurately predicted. From mat cooling data, it became evident that the asphalt concrete lift of 75 mm can be effectively compacted for about one hour (temperature ranging from 155-80 °C) with both steel roller and PTR. The temperature of 80 °C is generally regarded as the critical temperature at which no substantial compaction can be achieved by normal procedures of rolling.

Figure 11: The rate of asphalt mat cooling for a bound bituminous base made with coralline aggregates

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that the coralline aggregates can be used to produce durable, workable and cohesive asphalt concrete if properly designed as evidenced by the achieved volumetric data and the immersion index test results which gives an indication of the mix performance suitability. The immersion index is a measure of the asphalt mix resistance against moisture-induced damages. The retained stability of more than 90% is a direct indication that the coralline bituminous bound base is not likely to lose their strength due to ingress of water. Thus

guarantees that no de-bonding of the asphalt film from the aggregate surface is likely to occur due to moisture content.

If the aggregate design structure is properly selected, then the coralline asphalt mix stability, durability, stiffness and flexibility can be maintained throughout the pavement life. However, owing to the inherent variability of the coralline material, an extensive testing regime is required to allow the test results to be analysed statistically such that any unusual test results can be discerned and analysed.

The test results of the asphalt concrete made from the coralline aggregates need to be evaluated on a daily basis, and mix also needs frequent modification to accommodate the inherent variation of the coralline geo-material properties such as specific gravity and water absorption.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the experience accumulated during the mix design, production and placing the bituminous coralline base mix, the following is recommended:

1. The asphalt mixes made from the coral aggregates are more expensive to produce. The coralline material reduces the asphalt plant efficiency by about 20-30%. The analysis carried out during production of the coralline bituminous base revealed that the production of coralline base costs about 30-50 \$ more per ton compared to the asphalt made from the conventional aggregates. The increase in cost is caused by the reduction of plant efficiency as well as the excess bitumen required to achieve the desired volumetric properties.
2. The asphalt mix design should be carried out using oven aged samples to depict the actual expected delays to be experienced on-site. Furthermore, ageing of the asphalt concrete mix will allow the aggregate to absorb bitumen, enabling realistic computation of the effective binder content, VMA and air voids. If no delay is expected on site

- prior, then the sample should be aged for at least 2 hours before compacting the briquette for volumetric analysis.
3. The coral geo-material tends to degrade during drying and mixing and thus in most cases tends to produce an excess fine (i.e. passing 0.075 mm); therefore, the degree of degradation during drying and mixing should be quantified by assessing the target grading during the mix design and the resultant grading from the asphalt plant and the mix should be adjusted accordingly by either reducing the amount of sand in the mix or decreasing the amount filler in the mix.

REFERENCES

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